

1 **Discovery of diverse chimeric peptides in a eukaryotic proteome sets the stage for the**
2 **experimental proof of the mosaic translation hypothesis**

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27 **Running title**

28 Diverse chimeric peptides in a eukaryotic proteome

29 **Abbreviations**

30 altORF, alternative open reading frame; refORF, reference open reading frame; altProt,
31 alternative protein; refProt, reference protein; CP, chimeric peptide; PRF, programmed
32 ribosomal frameshifting; mRNA, messenger RNA; ncRNA, non-coding RNA; rRNA, ribosomal
33 RNA; tRNA, transfer RNA; CDS, coding sequence; UTR, untranslated region; aa, amino acids;
34 bp, base pairs; nt, nucleotides; MS, mass spectrometry

35 **Abstract**

36 The high complexity of eukaryotic organisms enabled their evolutionary success, which
37 became possible due to the diversification of eukaryotic proteomes. Various mechanisms
38 contributed to this process. Alternative splicing had the largest known impact among these
39 mechanisms: tens or hundreds of protein isoforms produced from a single genetic locus.

40 Earlier, we hypothesized that along with alternative splicing, a different but conceptually similar
41 mechanism creates novel versions of existing proteins in all eukaryotes. However, this
42 mechanism acts at the level of translation, where the novelty of an amino acid sequence is
43 achieved via multiple programmed ribosomal frameshifting. This mechanism, which is termed
44 mosaic translation, is very difficult to demonstrate even with the most up-to-date molecular
45 tools. Thus, it remained unnoticed so far. Using only a portion of all mass spectrometry
46 proteomic data generated from various organs of the model plant *Medicago truncatula*, we
47 attempted the first step toward the experimental proof of this hypothesis. Our original *in silico*
48 approach resulted in the discovery of two candidates for mosaic proteins (homologs of EF1 α
49 and RuBisCo) and 154 candidates for chimeric peptides. Chimeric peptides and polypeptides
50 are produced in the course of one ribosomal frameshifting event and may correspond to parts
51 of mosaic proteins. In addition, our analysis reveals the possibility of translation of chimeric
52 peptides from five ribosomal RNA transcripts, ten long non-coding RNA transcripts, and one
53 transfer RNA transcript. These findings are very novel and will be the basis for experimental
54 validation in future studies. In this work, we present multiple lines of indirect evidence that
55 support the validity of our *in silico* data.

56 **Keywords**

57 Chimeric peptide, programmed ribosomal frameshifting, alternative open reading frame,
58 elongation factor, RuBisCo; mosaic translation

59 **1. Introduction**

60 Recently, it has been recognized that eukaryotic transcripts have a polycistronic nature, which
61 revolutionized our understanding of the proteome complexity (Moulleron et al., 2016). The
62 central point in this paradigm-shifting development was the discovery of translated alternative
63 open reading frames (altORFs) and their inventory in the variety of organisms (Brunet et al.,
64 2019, 2021; Leblanc et al., 2024). These regions of transcripts can be defined as relatively
65 long stop-free sequences in any reading frame. Products of their translation, alternative
66 proteins (altProts), may resemble some annotated proteins or be entirely unique. In both
67 cases, they are thought to be an important source of protein novelty in the evolution (Orr et
68 al., 2020; Riegger and Caliskan, 2022; Ardern, 2023). AltORFs often overlap with annotated
69 coding sequences, also called reference ORFs (refORFs), or other altORFs located on the
70 same transcript (Moulleron et al., 2016; Orr et al., 2020). Earlier, high abundance of conserved
71 altORFs in plant transcriptomes prompted us to hypothesize that a mechanism by which the
72 information from overlapping ORFs is combined in continuous polypeptide molecules in the
73 course of multiple programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) may have importance in the
74 adaptability of organisms to internal and external conditions (Çakır et al., 2023). In contrast to
75 a chimeric peptide or polypeptide, which originates from a single PRF event per transcript,
76 with only a few known examples in prokaryotes (Blinkowa and Walker, 1990; Flower and
77 McHenry, 1990; Tsuchihashi and Kornberg, 1990; Chaijarasphong et al, 2016; Meydan et al.,
78 2017) and eukaryotes (Matsufuji et al., 1995; Clark et al., 2007; Ivanov and Atkins, 2007; Ren
79 et al., 2024), a peptide or polypeptide produced via two and more PRF events has a mosaic
80 nature because it combines translational products of multiple reading frames (Ketteler, 2012).
81 Thus, we refer to this mode of translation as mosaic translation. Mosaic Gag-Pro-Pol
82 polypeptides produced by this mechanism have been described in some viruses (Jacks, 1990;
83 Hatfield et al., 1992; Rex et al., 2019), which have to overlap their genes with high density for
84 the more complete usage of their limited genomic space. In contrast, this way of using the
85 coding potential of altORFs has not been anticipated to play an important role in eukaryotes,
86 probably because of their large genomes. To the best of our knowledge, only one study has
87 suggested the existence of mosaic proteins in eukaryotes (Ketteler, 2012). We took a long

88 step forward and proposed why mosaic translation may be a ubiquitous phenomenon with
89 fundamental importance in all domains of life. Our chief argument was the enormous biological
90 advantage that should result from the manifold expansion of protein-coding capacity. The
91 direct proof of this hypothesis is nearly impossible without a revolution in the read length of
92 protein sequencers. The plan to develop a long-read method by which mosaic proteins can
93 be discovered at a large scale has been mentioned by Timp and Timp (2020). It is based on
94 the nanopore sequencing principle, which proved to be very useful in long-read sequencing of
95 nucleic acids (Pugh, 2023). Despite very recent revolutionary developments in nanopore
96 sequencing of proteins, the long-read version of the method is still not available due to major
97 challenges. The first challenge is slowing down and stretching the long polypeptide molecules
98 during their transit through the nanopore. The second challenge is discriminating among
99 amino acids with different posttranslational modifications (Martin-Baniandres et al., 2023;
100 Wang et al., 2024). Due to the absence of any adequate alternative to the protein nanopore
101 sequencing, earlier, we proposed a strategy that can detect candidates for mosaic translation
102 based on available mass spectrometry (MS) proteomic data. If conserved and/or translated
103 altORFs overlap with refORFs, other altORFs, or both, possible PRF events that change the
104 translation from one frame to another can be modeled. Once the frameshifted sequences are
105 modeled, they can be used as a query database in the searches for corresponding MS
106 peptides in biological samples. This way, we proposed to detect individual chimeric peptides
107 in the first place. If two or more chimeric peptides validated by MS originate from the same
108 transcript, depending on the frameshift type and the distance between PRF sites, they can be
109 parts of a mosaic protein. Despite very large computational requirements, the principle
110 advantage of our approach is the use of MS proteomic data. For many organisms, such data
111 are already available in a very large amount (Perez-Riverol et al., 2022; Deutsch et al., 2023).
112 Up to 60% of high-quality peptides derived from eukaryotes that have been identified by MS
113 cannot be assigned to any genomic location (Ning et al., 2010; Pathan et al., 2017). A similar
114 problem has been found in assigning the minimal proteome of the smallest culturable
115 bacterium with only 729 ORFs (Lluch-Senar et al., 2016). Earlier, it was suggested that this
116 unmapped “dark” proteome could be composed of translational products of altORFs
117 (Mouilleron et al., 2016; Orr et al., 2020). A recent study in humans identified many thousands
118 of previously unknown peptides, so-called non-canonical ORFs (ncORFs), which further
119 emphasizes the true complexity of the proteome (Cao et al., 2024). We extend this idea to
120 mosaic peptides and proteins, which are made of altORF/ncORF translation blocks. Novel
121 PRF sites can be detected with ribosome profiling, or Ribo-Seq (Ingolia et al., 2011; Kiniry et
122 al., 2019, 2021; Richardson and Eddy, 2023). While Ribo-Seq-based information about
123 positions of the frameshifts is expensive and technically challenging to generate, it is also
124 indirect compared to the information deduced from MS proteomic reads. Many organisms
125 have no Ribo-Seq datasets deposited publicly, including the model plant *Medicago truncatula*.
126 Here we demonstrate the efficient application of our MS-based approach on three selected
127 proteomic datasets from *M. truncatula*. To our knowledge, this pilot study is the first attempt
128 to demonstrate the existence of mosaic peptides and proteins in a non-viral biological system.
129 Although we detected only two good candidates for mosaic translation in the selected three
130 datasets, this approach can be extended to other datasets of *M. truncatula* and MS data from
131 other organisms, which can ultimately lead to the discovery of the large number of mosaic
132 proteins. Importantly, in the course of this work, we also detected many chimeric peptides
133 previously unthought for a eukaryotic genome. We hope that the novelty of our observations
134 will ultimately bring chimeric and mosaic proteins into the spotlight and will motivate the
135 scientific community to apply our approach to other organisms, including humans.

136 **2. Material and methods**

137 **2.1. *In-silico* extraction and translation of altProts**

138 The *M. truncatula* genome assembly and annotated features (v. 5.1.7) were downloaded from
139 the *M. truncatula* genome portal MtrunA17r5.0-ANR (Pecrix et al., 2018;
140 <https://medicago.toulouse.inra.fr/MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/>). In each transcript, we identified
141 regions that are at least 60 base pairs long and do not contain any in-frame stop codons in
142 three reading frames. These regions were then translated into sequences of amino acids using
143 the standard genetic code. This way, we generated a query database of peptide and
144 polypeptide sequences (altProts), from which reference proteins (refProts) were eliminated
145 based on their identity to sequences from the annotated proteome. Input and output
146 sequences of the corresponding script are FASTA-formatted. The script supplies output
147 sequences with unique identifiers that contain the following information: locus identifier,
148 reading frame (three forward frames denoted as 1F to 3F), nucleotide coordinates of the
149 extracted region on the transcript (first base and last base), and the length of the extracted
150 region on the transcript in bases. The code for generating this query database will be published
151 elsewhere (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation).

152 **2.2. Sequence similarity searches using a protein reference database**

153 Each altProt was compared with entries from the reference protein database UniProt v.
154 2020_02 (UniProt Consortium, 2019) using DIAMOND v. 0.9.14 (Buchfink et al., 2021). To
155 build a DIAMOND search database using a “makedb” command, a single fasta-file was
156 generated from the downloaded and concatenated UniProt sequences. The following
157 parameters were used for the similarity searches: “max-target-seqs”, which is the maximum
158 number of hits, was set to zero; this setting enabled the report of all hits per query; the maximal
159 expect value was set to 10^{-3} ; to enable higher sensitivity of the searches, an option “more-
160 sensitive” was used. For efficient downstream analysis of significant hits, the following
161 information was recorded for each sequence with at least one hit: “qseqid”, “stitle”, “length”,
162 “pident”, “ppos”, “qcovhsp”, “evalue”, and the number of hits. The information on taxonomy of
163 all hits was recorded for in-depth phylogenetic analysis.

164 **2.3. Validation of altProts by MS proteomics**

165 We searched for mass spectra-derived peptides that match each *in-silico* generated altProt
166 with the aid of SearchGUI v. 4.0.41 (Barsnes & Vaudel, 2018) and its partner tool
167 PeptideShaker v. 2.0.33 (Vaudel et al., 2015). Three proteomic datasets publicly deposited at
168 the ProteomeXchange database (Deutsch et al., 2023) were used for this purpose:
169 PXD002692 (Marx et al., 2016), PXD013606 (Shin et al., 2021), and PXD022278 (Castañeda
170 et al., 2021), which contain nine, one, and six samples respectively (Supplementary Dataset
171 S1). ThermoRawFileParser v. 1.1.2 (Hulstaert et al., 2020) was employed for the conversion
172 of raw data from these three datasets to Mascot Generic Format (MGF). X!Tandem, MS-GF+,
173 OMSSA, and Comet search algorithms were used in all searches. The search database
174 consisted of the following three components: (1) *in-silico* translated altProts; (2) all annotated
175 refProts; and (3) the contaminant database known as cRAP (common Repository of
176 Adventitious Proteins), which was downloaded from the GPM resource (GPM: Generalized
177 Proteomics data Meta-analysis; <https://www.thegpm.org/crap/>). Validated altProts were
178 excluded from the analysis if they grouped with a refProt or a contaminant sequence (Related
179 Proteins). Carbamidomethylation of C was set to fixed modification, and acetylation of protein
180 N-termini and oxidation of M were set to variable modifications. Precursor and fragment
181 tolerance were set to 4.5 ppm and 20.0 ppm, respectively. At most, two missed cleavages
182 were allowed. False discovery rate (FDR) of 1% was used to validate peptide-spectrum
183 matches (PSMs), peptides, and proteins with target/decoy hit distribution. The decoy spectral
184 library was generated by *in-silico* reversing the collection of refProt, altProt, and contaminant
185 sequences. Software version-specific default settings were used for parameters that are not

186 mentioned here. The results of PeptideShaker confidence classification of the chimeric
187 peptides are available in Supplementary Dataset S1.

188 The inclusion of all mRNA-derived altProts in the analysis causes the inflation of the search
189 database (more than 840,000 after the inclusion of refProts, Supplementary Table S1), which
190 strongly affects the number of confident protein identifications (Li et al., 2016; Kumar et al.,
191 2017). To avoid the database inflation, a two-step MS search approach was used (Jagtap et
192 al., 2013). In the first step, the list of altProt was shuffled and split into ten chunks. Each chunk
193 was used as a search database, and proteins validated in this first step were subsequently
194 included in the second search. Because there were 16 organs/conditions in datasets
195 PXD002692, PXD013606, and PXD022278 combined and ten groups of the mRNA-derived
196 altProt sequences, 160 MS searches were conducted in the first step of the two-step approach
197 and 16 in the second step for these three datasets. The parameters of individual searches
198 were specified above. The two-step approach was not used for non-mRNA-derived altProts
199 because their relatively small number does not inflate the search database. Thus, a single-
200 step MS search protocol was used for those sequences. MS searches for ncRNA, rRNA, and
201 tRNA-derived altProts were conducted separately. Because there were 16 organs/conditions
202 in total in the three MS datasets combined, 16 MS searches were conducted for each group
203 of non-mRNA-derived altProts. All validated altProts were recorded for further analysis. The
204 MS datasets were also searched independently, for instance, validated proteins from dataset
205 PXD002692 were not combined with those from PXD013606 or PXD022278 for the search
206 database of the second step.

207 **2.4. Modeling of chimeric proteins for MS searches**

208 Throughout the text, we discriminate between terms “chimeric peptide” and “chimeric protein”.
209 Namely, we reserve the former term for short amino acid sequences deduced from MS
210 proteomics. In contrast, *in-silico* generated models for matching corresponding MS peptides
211 are referred to as chimeric protein models even though their actual length generally does not
212 exceed 40 amino acids in our study. This is meant to emphasize that these models may
213 represent longer chimeric sequences or fragments of mosaic proteins. We also use the term
214 “chimeric protein” in contexts where the length is not relevant.

215 Although our in-house script can use the list of any overlapping or non-overlapping ORFs on
216 the same transcript as a starting point, regardless of their conservation and translation status,
217 the number of chimeric protein models thus generated would be astronomic. For this reason,
218 we modeled chimeric proteins based on two lists of altProts. The first list contained altProts
219 validated by MS searches, and the second list contained so-called conserved altProts. The
220 definition of “conserved” in this case refers to the presence of at least one hit with at least 70%
221 identity (e-value below 0.001) in the global sequence similarity search using UniProt as a
222 reference protein database.

223 Each MS-validated and/or conserved altProt has a corresponding altORF with coordinates on
224 its transcript and locus information. Our chimeric protein modeling algorithm determines and
225 *in-silico* translates products of many possible PRF events that may occur if an altORF overlaps
226 with its refORF or other altORFs on the same transcript. We use the word combination “many
227 possible PRF events” instead of “all possible PRF events” to emphasize that some situations
228 were deliberately left beyond the scope of our analysis. For example, we considered only PRF
229 values -2, -1, +1, and +2, which correspond to the backward and forward slippage of
230 ribosomes, respectively, by one or two nucleotides, although “longer” events that cause the
231 frameshifting by up to six bases are known (Weiss et al., 1987; Yan et al. 2015). The reason
232 for focusing on the “shortest” PRF events and the simplest scenarios was the phenomenon of
233 the search database inflation (Li et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2017). In short, generating models

234 for all theoretically possible chimeric proteins is technically feasible with our algorithm.
235 However, it is counterproductive to include all the models into the analysis. Thus, we included
236 only situations that would serve as the most convincing illustration of chimeric translation
237 without inflating the MS search database. This explains why the settings for the generation of
238 chimeric models were not uniform for all cases but were tailored to specific scenarios
239 described in the corresponding software article (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation).
240 Furthermore, those settings depended on the location of the frameshift relative to the involved
241 ORFs (the 5'-end vs the 3'-end).

242 **2.5. Validation of chimeric protein models by MS proteomics**

243 The number of chimeric protein models derived from MS-validated altProts is moderate
244 (36,536) and does not cause inflation of the search database. In contrast, the models derived
245 from conserved altProts are numerous (533,569), which causes inflation of the search
246 database (see Section 4.3). Thus, similarly to the MS-validation of mRNA-derived altProts, the
247 models from the latter group were searched by the two-step MS approach, while the regular
248 MS searches were conducted for the validation of the former group. The validation of chimeric
249 models involved the same three MS datasets and the same pipeline as the validation of
250 altProts. The list of chimeric protein models derived from the conserved altProts was split into
251 ten chunks. Each chunk was searched separately in 16 organs/conditions in the first step.
252 Then, validated chimeric protein models were searched one more time (phase two of the two-
253 step approach). Validated models were recorded for further analysis. Because there were 16
254 organs/conditions in those three datasets, 160 and 16 MS searches were conducted in the
255 first and second steps of the two-step approach, respectively, for the models derived from
256 conserved altProts. Unlike in the altProt validation, altProts used for the modeling of chimeric
257 proteins were also included in the search database in addition to the refProt and cRAP
258 databases, which permitted the elimination of chimeric peptides identical to sequences of
259 altProts. This was necessary because some chimeric peptides were different from their
260 altProts or refProts by only one or two amino acids. If these different amino acids are
261 indistinguishable by MS, true altProts or true refProts may be categorized as chimeric proteins.
262 Validated chimeric protein models were excluded from the analysis if they grouped with an
263 altProt, a refProt, or a contaminant sequence. Thus, our final dataset (Supplementary Dataset
264 S1) is free from this ambiguity. Like with the validation of altProts, the three MS datasets were
265 searched independently.

266 **2.6. Visualization of chimeric MS peptides, chimeric protein models, mosaic proteins, 267 and their respective transcripts**

268 Sequences of MS-supported chimeric peptides were identified and manually mapped to their
269 transcripts in Geneious® v. 7.1 (Dotmatrix Ltd., MA, USA, <https://www.geneious.com>). The
270 location of each PRF event, its value (-2, -1, +1, or +2), type, and subtype (Supplementary
271 Dataset S1) were deduced manually. To create images of transcripts associated with each
272 PRF event, we calculated sizes and coordinates of each feature in Geneious® and then
273 converted them to distances in centimeters to be plotted. Transcript lengths were scaled to
274 either 10 cm or 20 cm in the images, depending on the purpose of each figure, so that
275 transcripts of two different lengths in nucleotides appear equal in lengths in the images. This
276 way, we unified visualization of transcripts that ranged from 84 bp to 10,214 bp.

277 **2.7. Protein folding predictions**

278 To estimate the proportion of potentially unstructured protein sequences in our collection of
279 putative chimeric peptides, and also to discriminate between sequences that fold into alpha-
280 helices and beta-sheets, we predicted their folding with ColabFold v1.5.2 (Mirdita et al., 2022)

281 and visualized it with ChimeraX v. 1.6.1 (Pettersen et al., 2004). The predictions were run in
282 the unrelaxed mode. Because MS peptides that support chimeric models are too short for
283 folding predictions (8-30 aa, Supplementary Dataset S1), we based the predictions on
284 chimeric models, which are longer than MS peptides. Five predictions per sequence were
285 made, out of which the top-score predictions, and in some cases strongly differing additional
286 predictions with a lower score, were depicted.

287 **2.8. Homology searches**

288 To identify homology groups within the dataset, transcript and protein sequences that
289 correspond to chimeric peptides were aligned with a Geneious[®] alignment tool, which is a
290 built-in option in the Geneious[®] software, and also with Clustal Omega (Sievers et al., 2011).
291 To identify small-scale local similarities among sequences, we employed the MEME (Multiple
292 EM for Motif Elicitation) software v. 5.4.1 (Bailey and Elkan, 1994; Bailey et al., 2015). In
293 addition, BLASTN and BLASTP tools (Altschul et al., 1990; Boratyn et al., 2013) and the *M.*
294 *truncatula* genome portal (Pecrix et al., 2018) were used for the identification of homology
295 groups based on shared subjects. The same tools were used for the annotation of transcripts
296 and translational products of refORFs and altORFs involved in the production of chimeric
297 peptides (Supplementary Dataset S1).

298 **2.9. Identification of alternative sources**

299 In searches for non-chimeric alternative sources of chimeric MS peptides, we used genomic,
300 repeat element, and transcript data from the *M. truncatula* genome portal (Pecrix et al., 2018),
301 50 selected RNA-Seq datasets of *M. truncatula* deposited at the Sequence Read Archive
302 (SRA) database (Leinonen et al., 2011; Katz et al., 2022), and the RNA-Seq-based gene
303 expression atlas of this organism (MtExpress v. 3, Carrere et al., 2021;
304 <https://medicago.toulouse.inrae.fr/GEA>). In-house scripts based on TBLASTN were used for
305 the similarity searches in this part of the study. MtExpress was also used for transcription
306 profiles of primary sources and the selection of the most likely alternative chimeric sources
307 listed in Supplementary Dataset S1. In searches for chimeric alternative sources, we used a
308 script that will be published separately as the area of its application is broad (Çakır et al.,
309 preprint in preparation). Transcript and repeat-element data from the newer version 5.1.9 of
310 the *M. truncatula* genome browser (Pecrix et al., 2018) were used in this analysis. Each
311 primary-source transcript was manually analyzed for differences between v. 5.1.7 and v. 5.1.9.
312 There were no sequence or length differences found between these two genome releases for
313 any of the primary-source transcripts.

314 **2.10. Statistical analysis**

315 To estimate the deviation from the randomness assumption in the relationships between
316 various features of chimeric peptides and their transcripts, we mostly employed the chi-square
317 tests for the association and the goodness-of-fit as conservative non-parametric tools. In some
318 cases, we used Pearson and Spearman correlation analyses along with corresponding t-tests
319 for the significance of their p-values. For the assessment of differences between BLASTP and
320 BLASTN-related characteristics of four RNA types (mRNA, ncRNA, rRNA, and tRNA),
321 Kholmogorov-Smirnov test was utilized in R (R Core Team, 2021). This test is an adequate
322 non-parametric procedure suitable for the comparisons of samples that have very different
323 variances and sizes. In cases where the application of the chi-square test was inappropriate
324 (at least one cell with an expected value below five), three alternative tests were used in R:
325 (1) the Fisher's exact test for more than one level and more than two proportions; (2) the Exact
326 Multinomial Test for one level and more than two proportions; (3) the Exact Binomial Test for
327 one level and two proportions. In some cases, indicated in supplementary figures, the exact

328 tests could not be run because of a large number of categories and/or very low values in
329 specific groups. An alpha-level of 5% was used as a significance threshold in all tests. The
330 default setting of all tests mentioned above is to calculate a two-sided p-value. Graphs for
331 supplementary figures were generated in Microsoft Excel and in some cases in R or SPSS®
332 Statistics v. 27.0 (IBM® Corporation, NY, USA, <https://www.ibm.com/products/spss-statistics>).

333 4. Results

334 4.1. The *M. truncatula* transcriptome contains thousands of altORFs with a 335 conservation signature

336 To enable a comprehensive study with potential for novel observations, we have not limited
337 our analysis to mRNA transcripts. We included three other RNA types that are classically
338 defined as non-coding: ncRNA, rRNA, and tRNA, which are among the longest of all known
339 RNA types (Palazzo and Lee, 2015; Boivin et al., 2019). With the same intention, we have not
340 limited our definition of an open reading frame (ORF) to transcript regions that start with or
341 contain the standard translation initiation codon AUG (Sieber et al., 2018). Here we define an
342 ORF as a stop-free region above certain length in any forward reading frame, which
343 conceptually has the potential to be translated to a short peptide or a longer chain of amino
344 acids. Eventually, this ORF definition proved to be useful as it led to the discovery of many
345 translated ORFs that do not start with an ATG or even contain no ATG at any position (results
346 not shown). On the other hand, the inclusion of non-coding RNA types allowed us to detect
347 chimeric peptides potentially translated from all the three groups of transcripts, including tRNA,
348 and non-chimeric altProts translated from ncRNA.

349 Because we planned to use the DIAMOND BLASTP analysis as a part of our detection
350 pipeline, we chose 60 nt as a minimal ORF length. This decision was conditioned by the
351 intrinsic limitations of the BLASTP algorithm in handling peptide sequences shorter than 20
352 aa (Altschul, 1991). The annotated transcriptome v. 5.1.7 of *M. truncatula* (Pecrix et al., 2018)
353 contains 875,356 altORFs longer than 59 nt, which correspond to putative altProts of 20 aa or
354 longer (Supplementary Table S1). We extracted these sequences by *in-silico* translation and
355 subjected them to the BLASTP analysis. AltProts that had at least one hit were retained for
356 further analysis if they passed the following threshold: e-value at most 0.001, percent amino
357 acid identity at least 70. There were 13,078 such sequences (Table 1), which we conditionally
358 call conserved altProts, although in reality their conservation is often limited to the *M.*
359 *truncatula* proteome. Table 1, Supplementary Figures S1-S5, and Supplementary Tables S1-
360 S4 illustrate details and statistics of the BLASTP results.

361 4.2. Three public MS proteomic datasets of *M. truncatula* provide evidence for 362 translation of 805 putative altProts

363 In parallel with the BLASTP analysis, all 875,356 putative altProts were analyzed for the
364 presence of corresponding MS spectra in three selected proteomic datasets of *M. truncatula*
365 (Marx et al., 2016; Shin et al., 2021; Castañeda et al., 2021). This analysis revealed 805
366 unique putative altProts with evidence for translation, 122 of which are also present in the list
367 of conserved altProts. Supplementary Figures S4 and S5 show distributions of the top-hit
368 percent identity and the number of hits, respectively, for the 122 conserved MS-supported
369 altProts. Most of the altProts detected by MS (720 unique sequences) correspond to mRNA
370 transcripts. However, we have also found 85 unique ncRNA-derived altProts supported by
371 MS. No validated non-chimeric MS peptides were found for rRNA-altProts and tRNA-altProts
372 (Supplementary Figure S6). In total, 16 biological samples contain MS peptides corresponding
373 to altProts. More than half of these peptides (573) were detected in just four samples: seeds

374 (155), 10-dpi nodules (147), flowers (136), and buds (135), which may point to the importance
375 of altProts in the reproduction and symbiotic nitrogen fixation (Supplementary Figure S6).

376 In the BLASTP analysis, the taxonomic status of the top-hit subject sequence may reflect the
377 degree of conservation of the query sequence among different organisms, especially if the
378 number of significant hits is small. In our analysis, 70, 65, and 39% of altProts have between
379 1 and 5 hits before the application of the 70% filter, after the filter, and in the set of conserved
380 MS-supported altProts, respectively. The corresponding median numbers of hits in these three
381 samples are 2, 2, and 16.5, which is rather low (Supplementary Figures S2, S3, and S5). This
382 indicates that, as a whole, altProts detected in our study do not share similarity with proteins
383 from many species but just a few. A very large portion of these altProts have the top-similarity
384 with proteins from *M. truncatula* itself or from other legume species (Supplementary Figure
385 S7). At the same time, the majority of MS-supported altProts (683 out of 805, which is ca.
386 85%) have no similarity with any annotated protein at all. On the other hand, percent amino
387 acid identity with the top hit is another parameter that may reflect the degree of conservation.
388 In our dataset (Supplementary Figure S1), median values of percent identity are very high,
389 which may point to the potential origin of many altProts from duplication events and
390 frameshifting mutations in the *M. truncatula* genome and its common ancestors with other
391 legume species. Percent identity reaches the maximum in tRNA-altProts (100%) followed by
392 rRNA-altProts (93.3%), which has also the highest median number of hits (Supplementary
393 Figure S1). Together with other parameters described in Table 1, these observations highlight
394 a very special role of tRNA and rRNA in genome evolution, which was proposed earlier (Root-
395 Bernstein and Root-Bernstein, 2015, 2016, 2019; Caetano-Anollés and Caetano-Anollés,
396 2016; de Farias et al., 2016).

397 **4.3. Modeling of chimeric proteins based on the combined evidence for conservation** 398 **and translation helped to validate MS peptides that match 156 chimeric models**

399 Our next goal was to generate chimeric models for matching them to peptides present in MS
400 proteomic samples. We searched for altORFs that overlap with annotated coding sequences
401 (refORFs) and/or each other among altORFs of 13,780 conserved and/or translated altProts
402 (13,078 conserved + 805 translated - 103 both conserved and translated, see Table 1 and
403 also Supplementary Figures S4 and S6). Upon detection of such overlapping ORFs, they were
404 used for the modeling of many possible PRF positions at which the translational switch can
405 occur. Four PRF categories are considered in this study: -2, -1, +1, and +2. These symbols
406 indicate the ribosomal movement back (-) or forth (+) by the corresponding number of
407 nucleotides. To explore a possibility of unconventional PRF events that bridge closely spaced
408 non-overlapping (adjacent) ORFs, we also included ORFs that were separated by 1-10 nt. For
409 this category of ORF pairs, we have modeled chimeric proteins using only forward frameshifts,
410 from +1 to +10. In some cases, the software generated models that incorporated stop codons.
411 Such models were eliminated from the analysis or shortened by a few amino acids. In this
412 process, 570,105 models of chimeric proteins were generated, 36,536 of which were modeled
413 with MS-supported altProts and the remaining 533,569 ones used conserved putative altProts
414 as the basis (redundant numbers of models shown in Supplementary Table S5). These models
415 were subjected to the search for matching MS peptides using the same three datasets as for
416 the identification of translated altORFs. This search delivered translation evidence for 156
417 putative chimeric proteins, 20 of which were modeled with MS-supported altProts and 135 with
418 conserved putative altProts. One of these sequences, chimeric protein 78 (CP78) was
419 modeled with an altProt that was conserved and MS-supported at the same time
420 (Supplementary Dataset S1). None of chimeric protein models generated with non-
421 overlapping adjacent ORFs (Scenario 3 in Çakır et al., preprint in preparation) matched
422 validated MS peptides in our study. It should be noted that refORFs were assumed to be

423 translated in this analysis. However, if a chimeric protein was modeled with a conserved
424 altORF that overlaps with a refORF, it was scored as modeled with a conserved altORF. This
425 definition was appropriate because our primary goal was to study translation of altORFs,
426 whereas refORF translation is an expected condition. Supplementary Dataset S2 illustrates
427 the details of each chimeric model, its matching MS peptide, position, type, and value of PRF,
428 and positions of involved ORFs relative to their transcripts. Supplementary Dataset S3
429 contains sequences of 156 chimeric models, their matching MS peptides, and corresponding
430 145 transcripts with detailed annotation of features. Supplementary Dataset S1 provides a
431 very comprehensive summary of many aspects of the identified chimeric proteins and permits
432 easy cross-comparison of various categories.

433 After the analysis was completed, we realized the existence of two sources of redundancy
434 among 570,105 models of chimeric proteins. Firstly, chimeric models that corresponded to
435 103 conserved MS-supported altORFs were counted twice because we conducted the
436 modeling separately for conserved and translated altORFs. Secondly, chimeric models in
437 which PRF events involved only altORFs were counted twice, so our pipeline generated two
438 identical sets of models for each altORF. In the first set, altORF1 (the upstream one) was
439 considered as a refORF, and in the other set, altORF2 (the downstream one) was treated as
440 a refORF. These two sources of redundancy were subsequently eliminated from the pipeline
441 (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation). Accordingly, corresponding non-redundant counts of
442 chimeric models were recorded for different altORF types, PRF values, RNA types, MS
443 proteomic studies (Supplementary Tables S6-S9), and also for different chromosomal
444 locations (see Section 4.5.9 in Supplementary Results). In supplementary figures, expected
445 counts based on the distribution of chimeric models were calculated using non-redundant
446 numbers of chimeric models per category without models that come from non-overlapping
447 ORFs (Supplementary Table S9). These models that correspond to the group “other” were
448 excluded from the calculations of expected counts because none of them received MS-
449 support. It should be noted that the inclusion of 99,355 duplicated chimeric models in our MS
450 search process (ca. 17% of 570,105) is unlikely to have affected the efficiency of detection
451 because models with identical sequences were combined by the analysis software into related
452 protein groups.

453 **4.4. The detection of eight transcripts associated with multiple MS-supported chimeric** 454 **peptides enabled the discovery of first candidates for mosaic translation**

455 Our primary analysis revealed the presence of eight transcripts each associated with more
456 than one frameshifting event (Supplementary Dataset S4). We also conducted a nearly
457 exhaustive search for genomic and transcript regions that can potentially produce any of the
458 156 detected chimeric MS peptides, with or without PRF involved. We call them alternative
459 sources throughout the manuscript. That additional analysis indicated conservation of some
460 chimeric peptides within the *M. truncatula* genome and pointed to other transcripts with
461 multiple frameshifting potential. Transcripts mentioned in this section are referred to as primary
462 sources (145 transcripts). They will be the focus of our main discussion.

463 Among eight transcripts with multiple frameshifting potential, six were annotated as mRNA.
464 They have two or three MS-deduced putative PRF sites per transcript, most of which are
465 located within the boundaries of their refORFs (except for MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341, CP90
466 and CP91). Two non-mRNA transcripts are MtrunA17_MTg0490971 (ncRNA, CP150 and
467 CP151) and MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291 (rRNA, CP88 and CP89). Each of them has two
468 putative PRF sites per transcript (Supplementary Dataset S4).

469 Next, we analyzed the sequence context of each chimeric peptide in this group, with the focus
470 on the PRF value, frames involved, the distance between the PRF sites, and the presence of

471 in-frame stop codons between the PRF sites. This analysis suggested that six transcripts out
472 of the eight are unlikely candidates for mosaic translation unless additional MS-supported PRF
473 sites are found for those transcripts. For example, in MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811 (mRNA, CP16,
474 CP17, and CP18), all the three PRF sites have the same PRF value (+1). In addition, they
475 belong to the same PRF type (1→2) and PRF subtype (a→r). Supplementary Dataset S1
476 explains the definitions of these categories. Such arrangement of PRF sites does not support
477 the possibility of mosaic translation from MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811. In
478 MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341 (mRNA, CP90 and CP91), two PRF sites are separated by 1,373
479 nt. Although the first PRF site has value -2 and the second one +2, both PRF events in this
480 transcript start from frame 3, which is incompatible with the production of one continuous
481 mosaic protein of the category that we called short round trip (Çakır et al., 2023). Furthermore,
482 there are 25 stop codons in frame 1 between the first and the second PRF site, which would
483 require the discovery of many additional chimeric peptides to form a continuous mosaic
484 “bridge” between the two PRF sites. Unlike other transcripts in this dataset,
485 MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 (mRNA, CP23 and CP24) and MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 (mRNA,
486 CP98, CP99, and CP100) are good candidates for mosaic translation (Figure 1 and
487 Supplementary Dataset S4). The annotated product of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 is a protein-
488 synthesizing GTPase. The transcript of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 has 73.5% nucleotide
489 identity with an alternative-source transcript of CP24 and CP101, MtrunA17_Chr6g0458111
490 (elongation factor 1-alpha named *MtEF1A1* in Xu et al., 2023) and the primary-source
491 transcript of CP101, MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091. *MtEF1A1* is the key regulator of translation
492 involved in abiotic stress responses and adaptation to the environment.
493 MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091 is occasionally used as a housekeeping gene for RT-PCR analysis
494 (Gomez et al., 2009; Jiang et al., 2018) despite suboptimal stability of its expression in various
495 tissues (Kakar et al., 2008). The second candidate for mosaic translation,
496 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, encodes a ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase (RuBisCo), which is
497 the major enzyme in photosynthesis (Chen et al., 2023). Despite completely different putative
498 cellular functions, our study indicates that these two transcripts, MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071
499 and MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, have much in common. The first PRF site in both transcripts
500 has the same value -2, the same PRF type (2→3), and the same PRF subtype (r→a).
501 Likewise, the second PRF site shares the same characteristics in those two transcripts: the
502 PRF value +2, the PRF type (3→2), and the PRF subtype (a→r). The distance between the
503 two PRF sites is only 81 nt in the transcript of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 and 60 nt in
504 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461. Neither have in-frame stop codons between the two PRF sites,
505 which makes them perfect candidates for producing mosaic proteins of the short round trip
506 category (Çakır et al., 2023).

507 According to our study, MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 is expected to produce one 448 aa long
508 mosaic protein, which is of the same length as the annotated product. However, this mosaic
509 protein contains 28 aa entirely different from the annotated protein in the middle of the
510 sequence (Figure 1A, Supplementary Dataset S5). This segment introduced by putative
511 mosaic translation does not disrupt the overall three-dimensional structure of the protein, as
512 predicted by ColabFold, but rather modifies it (Supplementary Figure S8). This is not very
513 surprising because the NCBI BLASTP analysis of the conserved altProt that donates its
514 sequence to the mosaic protein has the top similarity to elongation factor 1-alpha from *M.*
515 *truncatula*.

516 In contrast to MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071, the second likely candidate for mosaic translation,
517 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, is expected to produce two 177 aa long mosaic proteins, which are
518 of the same length as the annotated RuBisCo. Because of the presence of the second -2 PRF
519 site only one nucleotide away from the first site, the two mosaic proteins of
520 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 differ by just one amino acid. One mosaic isoform contains 22 aa

521 in the middle of the sequence that are entirely different from the annotated protein (Figure 1B,
522 Supplementary Dataset S5). The other mosaic isoform contains the same segment but one
523 amino acid shorter at the left side (21 aa different from the annotated product, Figure 1C,
524 Supplementary Dataset S5). Like in the case with MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071, these segments
525 introduced by putative mosaic translation somewhat modify the three-dimensional structure of
526 the protein, as predicted by ColabFold (Supplementary Figures S9 and S10). The translational
527 product of the conserved altORF involved in the putative PRF events of both mosaic isoforms
528 is similar to RuBisCo from another legume species, *Arachis duranensis* (peanut). Thus, it is
529 possible that this altORF emerged via a frameshifting mutation, which is older than in the case
530 of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071. The complete ColabFold prediction files corresponding to the
531 annotated and mosaic proteins of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 and MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461
532 can be found in Supplementary Dataset S6.

533 Interestingly, the putative PRF sites in transcripts mentioned in this section repeat in distinct
534 groups. Namely, three transcripts, MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071, MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, and
535 MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341, have the first PRF site with the value -2 followed by a +2 PRF site.
536 The other group, MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, and
537 MtrunA17_MTg0490971, have repeated +1 sites. The only rRNA transcript in this group,
538 MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291, has repeated -1 sites. MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151 has no particular
539 pattern of PRF sites, which is an exception in this subset of transcripts (Supplementary
540 Dataset S4). These non-random observations may reflect the biological relevance of this
541 grouping.

542 **4.5. Multiple significant associations between various parameters of the dataset reject** 543 **the null hypothesis of its artifactual origin**

544 Our hypothesis about the mosaic nature of proteins produced by MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071
545 and MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 relies on the validity of the entire dataset. So far, MS
546 proteomics is the most powerful and accurate large-scale method for the discovery of new
547 proteins (Timp and Timp, 2020; Bennett et al., 2023; Messner et al., 2023). Despite its unique
548 status among currently available methods, MS-based detection of peptides and proteins is
549 inherently prone to false discoveries even when the standard procedures for their control are
550 implemented, especially in proteogenomics (Aggarwal et al., 2022; Ebadi et al., 2023). In our
551 study, we used a standard FDR of 1% as a threshold. However, because of the very large
552 search space used for the detection of chimeric peptides (more than half-million of chimeric
553 protein models, Supplementary Table S5), we had to apply a two-step search procedure.
554 Since the primary purpose of this approach is to lower the rate of false negatives (Jagtap et
555 al., 2013), it is likely to be associated with more difficult control over FDR. To address this
556 known weakness of the large-scale search for matching MS peptides, we conducted a very
557 comprehensive analysis of chimeric peptide features summarized in Supplementary Dataset
558 S1. Our intention was to detect significant relationships between features that are not
559 compatible with the null hypothesis about the randomness of the dataset. If the various
560 features were occurring randomly, it would suggest that the 156 validated chimeric peptides
561 might be false discoveries. Much of the data described in Figures 2-8, Supplementary Figures
562 S11-S62 (see Supplementary Results), and discussed below passed statistical tests.
563 Collectively, our statistical analysis revealed a clear deviation from the randomness
564 assumption. Thus, the detected sequences must have biological relevance.

565 **5. Discussion**

566 **5.1. Old is gold: MS proteomics can help reveal the existence of mosaic proteins in** 567 **the absence of methodology for long-read protein sequencing**

568 Earlier, we proposed that multiple PRF may play an important role in the adaptability of
569 organisms. The versatility of their proteomes may have been greatly expanded via the
570 production of polypeptides that incorporate translation products of different reading frames.
571 We refer to this hypothetical mechanism as mosaic translation (Çakır et al., 2023).
572 Experimental demonstration of this mechanism is a major challenge for a number of reasons.
573 They are associated with technical limitations of the protein detection methods. The chief
574 group of methods is based on MS proteomics. These methods infer the presence of long
575 continuous polypeptide sequences via the detection of their short fragments (7-35 aa, Swaney
576 et al., 2010). Unfortunately, this methodology permits the identification of only a small fraction
577 of non-canonical peptides actually present in a sample. Many biologically relevant peptides
578 that are expressed at a low level and/or have small size remain undetected by MS proteomics,
579 which does not reflect their instability or the lack of biological importance (Wacholder and
580 Carvunis, 2023). Unequivocal demonstration of the mosaic nature of a protein requires long
581 sequencing reads. Recently, a breakthrough in the development of nanopore-based
582 sequencing of proteins has been reported (Martin-Baniandres et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024).
583 Still, the current state of this methodology is too far from offering significant help with the
584 detection of long continuous mosaic polypeptides in a complex mixture of amino acid
585 sequences. In the absence of any alternative to MS-based proteomics, we decided to mine
586 the existing MS proteomic datasets for fragments of putative mosaic proteins that we modeled
587 using an original script (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation). Two types of data were used as
588 inputs for the script: (1) altProts that have a conservation signature based on the global
589 sequence similarity searches and (2) altProts that have matching MS-validated peptides
590 regardless of their conservation signature. Due to the nature of MS proteomics as a detection
591 strategy (Wacholder and Carvunis, 2023), 156 chimeric peptides reported here likely
592 represent only “the tip of an iceberg”, in which the hidden part is awaiting discovery.

593 **5.2 Main findings and arguments for their validity**

594 Upon the detection of 156 MS peptides that match chimeric models, we found that some of
595 them could be mapped to the same transcripts. This way, we discovered eight transcripts
596 associated with multiple PRF events, two or three per transcript. Based on the PRF value and
597 type, we showed that two of these transcripts are good candidates for the production of mosaic
598 proteins (Figure 1). One of them corresponds to a putative protein-synthesizing GTPase,
599 which is a close homolog of elongation factor alpha (MtEF1 α). The other one encodes a
600 putative ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase (RuBisCo), which is an enzyme central to
601 photosynthesis. Intriguingly, both putative mosaic proteins involve the same PRF events: the
602 first -2 frameshift changes translation from frame 2 (refORF) to frame 3 (altORF). The second
603 +2 frameshift brings translation back to the refORF located in frame 2. We think the exact
604 correspondence between these two PRF events in completely unrelated transcripts argues for
605 a biological reason for this conservation. The discovery of two strikingly convergent transcripts
606 that are likely to produce mosaic proteins in our non-viral system is highly novel and
607 unexpected. So far, mosaic proteins produced via PRF are known exclusively in viruses
608 (Jacks, 1990; Hatfield et al., 1992; Ketteler, 2012; Rex et al., 2019). This is the main finding of
609 our study. The remaining six transcripts with multiple PRF sites can also be candidates for
610 mosaic translation because additional PRF events associated with these transcripts can be
611 found in the future.

612 Ideally, MS peptides matching a mosaic protein must be long enough to include both PRF
613 sites. Due to the short read length of the current MS technology (7-35 aa, Swaney et al., 2010),
614 putative mosaic proteins produced by MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 and
615 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 have no matching MS peptides that would join the products of
616 individual PRF sites. However, the gap in the MS peptide coverage is fairly small: 16 aa for

617 MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 and only 6 aa for MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, which may indicate
618 that the peptides are indeed part of a continuous mosaic sequence (Figure 1, Supplementary
619 Dataset S5). These short distances between MS peptides permit testing the effects of
620 corresponding synthetic mosaic proteins *in vivo*. In addition, due to these short distances,
621 generation of MS proteomic data from the same samples using different digestive enzymes
622 could potentially yield peptide “bridges” that span the gaps in the peptide coverage. This would
623 serve as indirect evidence for continuity. Nevertheless, it is possible that MS peptides
624 corresponding to the PRF sites of these transcripts are translated individually as chimeric non-
625 mosaic sequences. On one hand, this possibility is supported by the existence of alternative
626 sources of these peptides. On the other hand, while three MS peptides that correspond to
627 putative PRF sites in MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 were all detected in the same organ (buds),
628 two MS peptides of MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 were found in two different organs (one in seeds
629 and the other one in leaves). Given the ambiguity associated with these multi-PRF sequences,
630 the following three scenarios are not mutually exclusive: (1) chimeric peptides are produced
631 individually from the same transcript; (2) chimeric peptides are produced individually from two
632 or more different transcripts; (3) chimeric peptides are produced in the course of mosaic
633 translation as parts of a continuous amino acid sequence from one transcript or multiple
634 transcripts. Dedicated wet lab studies are required for discrimination between these scenarios.
635 Despite the lack of solid proof, MS peptides corresponding to MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 and
636 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 provide the first experimental hint for a possibility of mosaic
637 translation in a non-viral system. Thus, they deserve close investigation in *M. truncatula*, which
638 will pave the avenue toward the discovery of mosaic proteins in other organisms. Our
639 methodology, in combination with parallel multi-enzyme digestion of protein samples for MS,
640 is likely to reveal many more candidates for mosaic proteins.

641 Our study provides unique information of fundamental importance in several other respects.
642 Firstly, the discovery of the large number of chimeric peptides in a non-viral system is another
643 novel outcome of our work because only a few chimeric peptides have so far been known
644 outside the viral kingdom: at least three in bacteria (Blinkowa and Walker, 1990; Flower and
645 McHenry, 1990; Tsuchihashi and Kornberg, 1990; Chaijarasphong et al, 2016; Meydan et al.,
646 2017) and at least three in eukaryotes (Matsufuji et al., 1995; Clark et al., 2007; Ivanov and
647 Atkins, 2007; Ren et al., 2024). In this respect, our results agree with the prediction according
648 to which as much as 10% of genes in a eukaryotic genome can be associated with PRF
649 (Ketteler, 2012). A parallel study in the human published very recently reached similar
650 conclusions (Ren et al., 2024; see Section 5.7). Secondly, the inclusion of non-mRNA
651 transcript types into our search pipeline revealed an entirely novel possibility. It showed that
652 MS-supported PRF events can be detected in ncRNA, rRNA, and even tRNA transcripts, all
653 of which are traditionally considered non-coding. Although still very exotic, the ability to serve
654 as a template for translation has already been demonstrated for ncRNA (Ingolia et al., 2011;
655 Ruiz-Orera and Albà, 2019; Zaheed et al., 2021), rRNA (Hashimoto et al., 2001; Maximov et
656 al., 2002), pre-miRNA (Wang et al., 2014; Couzigou et al., 2016), and pre-siRNA (Yoshikawa
657 et al., 2016). However, no information of this type has ever been reported for tRNA. At the
658 same time, to the best of our knowledge, PRF events have never been detected in any non-
659 mRNA transcript so far. Thus, our work sends several important messages that require close
660 attention.

661 Naturally, the presence of several non-ordinary findings in one computational MS proteomics-
662 based study raises doubts about the validity of the entire dataset. Thus, let us set our zero-
663 hypothesis as follows: the dataset is the collection of false-positives obtained due to the
664 difficulty of controlling false discovery rate when the procedure involves a very large search
665 database. The detailed manual analysis of various parameters (Supplementary Dataset S1)
666 in conjunction with stringent statistical procedures clearly indicates that most observations are

667 non-random and most associations are significant. This concerns not one or two parameters
668 but several dozens of various aspects. We summarized 37 of the most obvious significant
669 observations in Supplementary Dataset S29. Supplementary Dataset S30 lists 14 of the most
670 relevant significant associations. Taken together, these findings speak strongly against the
671 null-hypothesis, which indicates our data have biological relevance despite the high false
672 discovery rate expected for an MS proteomics-based study.

673 **5.3. RNA-Seq data as a support for chimeric nature of MS-validated peptides**

674 Another major concern associated with the discovery of highly novel peptide sequences is
675 their true origin. Can our chimeric peptides have alternative sources that do not involve PRF?
676 Using genomic DNA as a basis, we found that one chimeric peptide in our dataset, CP80, can
677 potentially be produced from two genomic loci with unknown translation status. However,
678 these loci are not transcribed, which makes them unlikely non-chimeric sources of the peptide
679 identical to CP80 (see Sections 4.7.1 and 4.7.3 in Supplementary Results). Alternative splicing
680 events such as exon skipping or intron retention, along with the products of RNA editing and
681 natural polymorphisms, can also potentially mimic chimeric peptides. Using the collection of
682 individual reads from 50 relevant RNA-Seq runs, we demonstrate that only one to four MS-
683 validated chimeric peptides (CP54, CP93, CP140, and CP148, or CP54 alone) could originate
684 from unusual versions of native transcripts without PRF. Contrary to our predictions
685 summarized in Supplementary Dataset S1, none of these peptides is likely to be produced via
686 alternative splicing (Supplementary Datasets S18 and S19).

687 **5.4 The existence of potential alternative sources is a challenge for the functional** 688 **analysis of chimeric proteins**

689 Because of the chimeric nature of MS-validated peptides in our dataset and their short length
690 typical for an MS study, many of them can have multiple origins (Supplementary Datasets S1
691 and S22 to S24). This genetic redundancy will make it very difficult to study their functions by
692 conventional loss-of-function methods such as insertional mutagenesis. Conceptually, RNA
693 interference (RNAi) can be used to downregulate a group of related transcripts (Mello and
694 Conte, 2004). Alternative sources of chimeric peptides in our study share a limited similarity,
695 which may permit their simultaneous silencing (as can be judged from their annotation,
696 Supplementary Dataset S24). Nevertheless, construction of multiple mutants may be required
697 to learn the loss-of-function phenotypes of these loci. Moreover, demonstration of individual
698 phenotypes for a refProt, altProts, and a chimeric protein(s) derived from a given transcript
699 will require complementation of null-mutants with constructs in which these proteins are
700 disabled differentially. Using an in-house script (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation), we
701 conducted a comprehensive inventory of genetic loci that can potentially produce chimeric
702 peptides identified in our study. This inventory is crucial for understanding the biological roles
703 of chimeric proteins. At the same time, ca. 58% of chimeric peptides reported here have
704 unique sources, which means they can be functionally characterized without generation of
705 multiple mutants. Based on the analysis of expression profiles, only 31 chimeric peptides out
706 of 156 (ca. 20%) can have alternative sources at least as likely as their primary sources
707 (Supplementary Dataset S1). Thus, it is possible that most of the 145 transcripts that are
708 denoted as primary sources in our study are indeed the main or even the only contributors to
709 the translation of these peptides. This possibility is supported by numerous significant
710 associations observed at the level of transcripts and genomic DNA of the primary-source loci
711 (e.g., Figure 3, 4, 5, and 8, Supplementary Figures S11-S15 and S50-S62). These
712 observations cannot be expected under an assumption that translation of chimeric peptides
713 detected in this study occurs mainly or exclusively from other transcripts (alternative sources).
714 A recent discovery of the promotive effect of synthetic complementary peptides on the

715 expression of matching transcripts offers a unique opportunity for studying mosaic and
716 chimeric proteins (Ormaney et al., 2023). Using synthetic versions of these proteins, one can
717 study the gain-of-function phenotypes associated not with a specific locus but with all loci that
718 actually contribute to the production of a mosaic or chimeric protein.

719 **5.5. Four genetic loci associated with the production of chimeric peptides in *M.*** 720 ***truncatula* have been in the focus of functional studies**

721 In the course of our work, we realized the importance of learning if any genes listed as primary
722 or alternative sources of chimeric peptides have already been studied by loss-of-function
723 approaches. Like in the case of altProts, chimeric proteins are expected to introduce ambiguity
724 to the interpretation of any genetic study. In the absence of knowledge about an altProt or a
725 chimeric protein translated along with a refProt, naturally, any mutant phenotype linked to the
726 locus is automatically attributed to the loss-of-function of a refProt. Incorrectly inferred
727 phenotype-genotype relationships can have dramatic consequences for efforts to cure genetic
728 diseases or develop a more resistant/more productive crop. To address this important task,
729 we have conducted a nearly comprehensive analysis of more than a thousand of loss-of-
730 function studies in *M. truncatula* that were published since the time of its advent as a model
731 organism (Barker et al., 1990). By January 2024, these studies involved at least 627 genetic
732 loci. To our surprise, only two genes from our primary-source list have been in the focus of
733 such studies so far. One of them is a sucrose synthase gene *MtSUCS1* (CP80,
734 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011). Antisense-mediated transcript knockdown of *MtSUCS1* leads to
735 the defects in symbiotic nitrogen fixation and arbuscular mycorrhizal symbiosis (Baier et al.,
736 2007, 2010). The other gene is a cytokinin oxidase/dehydrogenase *MtCKX6*, which was
737 targeted by insertional mutagenesis using tobacco retrotransposon *Tnt1*. The phenotype of
738 the *Mtckx6* mutants was analyzed in the context of root development. It turned out to be not
739 different from the phenotype of wild-type plants (Wang et al., 2021). One gene listed among
740 two alternative sources of CP104 was targeted by RNAi. It encodes a pathogenesis-related
741 protein MtPR10-5 (MtrunA17_Chr4g0067951). Downregulation of this gene together with four
742 likely off-target loci resulted in reduced colonization and suppressed infection by an oomycete
743 pathogen *Aphanomyces euteiches* (Colditz et al., 2007; Samac et al., 2011). Our meta-
744 analysis of publications on 627 loci targeted by at least one loss-of-function study does not
745 include genes analyzed exclusively via gain-of-function approaches. However, one such study
746 is worth mentioning here because it was conducted on an alternative source of two chimeric
747 peptides, CP24 and CP101 (MtrunA17_Chr6g0458111). This locus is among six possible
748 sources of these CPs, all of which are annotated as protein-synthesizing GTPases, including
749 a qRT-PCR housekeeping gene *MtEF1* (Gomez et al., 2009; Jiang et al., 2018).
750 Overexpression of MtrunA17_Chr6g0458111 named *MtEF1A1* in the original study renders
751 transgenic plants of *M. truncatula* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* more salt-tolerant (Xu et al., 2023).
752 It may be interesting to clarify whether the reported phenotypes of these genes can be
753 attributed to their refProts, chimeric peptides, or both.

754 The scarcity of previously studied genes in our dataset can probably be explained by the fact
755 that most of the 145 transcripts have transcription profiles not specific to a particular biological
756 process (Supplementary Datasets S1 and S27). In contrast, functional genomics studies
757 naturally focus on genes with process-specific or organ-specific transcription profiles.

758 **5.6. Chimeric sequences may be important for symbiotic nitrogen fixation and seed** 759 **development**

760 Nearly one quarter of chimeric peptides in our study were identified in nodule samples.
761 Together with chimeric peptides found in seeds, they make up 41% of the dataset (64
762 sequences, Supplementary Dataset S1, Supplementary Figure S36). This overrepresentation

763 of two biological processes may have technical reasons: we cannot meaningfully compare
764 abundances of validated proteins in different samples even if they are prepared by the same
765 group (Supplementary Figures S6 and S36). However, it may also point to important biological
766 roles of altORFs and chimeric peptides in symbiotic nitrogen fixation and seed development
767 along with other biological processes. Although we do not know if the detected MS peptides
768 represent short sequences or are fragments of long proteins, it should be noted that symbiotic
769 nitrogen fixation is known to involve short peptides for its regulation (Van de Velde et al., 2010;
770 Djordjevic et al., 2015; Kereszt et al., 2018; Roy and Müller, 2022; Ito et al., 2024; Roy et al.,
771 2024). Among chimeric peptides detected in multiple samples, the largest number of
772 sequences was shared by nodule and seed samples (eight chimeric peptides, Supplementary
773 Figure S38). This moderate association is surprising in the context of our study because seed
774 development and biological nitrogen fixation are processes expected to have only a limited
775 overlap in gene expression (Benedito et al., 2008; Mergaert et al., 2020). This is further
776 supported by the fact that only two genes out of 627 targeted by at least one loss-of-function
777 approach in *M. truncatula* (as of January 2024) are likely to have the roles in both processes:
778 MtCYP15a (Sheokand et al., 2005) and MtNOOT2 (Magne et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022;
779 Liu et al., 2023). On the other hand, root and nodule samples could be expected to have much
780 overlap in the abundance of peptides based on similarities in gene expression (Benedito et
781 al., 2008; Mergaert et al., 2020). Contrary to this expectation, roots share only three chimeric
782 peptides with nodules (Supplementary Dataset S1). Observations summarized in this section
783 warrant dedicated functional studies on our candidate loci. Differential mutagenesis-based
784 analyses of refProts and corresponding chimeric peptides from our dataset may provide useful
785 insights into molecular mechanisms shared by nodules and seeds.

786 **5.7. Our data complement a very recent MS-based study conducted on human** 787 **samples**

788 In this section, we would like to mention a very remarkable study that was published during
789 the preparation of our manuscript. Ren and associates (2024) discovered at least 405 unique
790 chimeric peptides in 32 diverse human samples not associated with any pathological
791 condition. These peptides correspond to 454 loci, all of which have naturally occurring repeat
792 codon sequences at the putative PRF sites. This group not only provided evidence for the
793 presence of such peptides in multiple samples but also functionally characterized one of the
794 loci, which encodes a histone deacetylase HsHDAC1. This study is very important because it
795 shows how widespread PRF can be in eukaryotic organisms. Although our work has a similar
796 goal and methodology, it does not duplicate the data of Ren et al. (2024). The studies are
797 different in a few principle points and thus are complementary. Firstly, none of 156 chimeric
798 peptides reported here originate from loci with repeated codons at the site of putative PRF.
799 Secondly, our dataset contains a homolog of *HsHDAC1*, which is a gene encoding a histone
800 deacetylase MtHDA9 (MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401, CP81). It also contains a few other loci
801 associated with histone deacetylase activity and histones in general (Supplementary Dataset
802 S1). Transcripts of *HsHDAC1* and *MtHDA9* share only ca. 57% nucleotide identity, and their
803 PRF sites do not coincide in the alignment. Thirdly, while the availability of many MS proteomic
804 datasets for the human permitted the identification of chimeric peptides across very many
805 samples, the *M. truncatula* datasets are still very limited. Thus, only 27 chimeric peptides out
806 of 156 (ca. 17%) were identified in more than one sample. This presents a major technical
807 limitation of our study along with the absence of wet lab validation of our candidate peptides.
808 However, in a few other aspects, our work has a broader scope and offers additional points of
809 novelty. For example, our methodology is conceptually open to the detection of PRF events
810 *de novo*, with no prior knowledge about similarity of PRF sites to already characterized cases.
811 Along with this principle difference, our dataset is not limited to chimeric peptides produced by
812 “short” PRF events (-1 and +1). It includes many sequences that require “long” frameshifts (-

813 2 and +2) for their generation, namely ca. 53%. Next, our dataset includes three non-mRNA
814 transcript types, which constitute ca. 12% of the sequences. Importantly, our study had the
815 goal of detecting multiple occurrence of PRF sites per transcript, which resulted in the
816 discovery of 15 non-RE and eight RE loci potentially associated with multiple frameshifting.
817 Lastly, there is a major difference in the way we considered alternative sources of chimeric
818 sequences. Namely, along with the exclusion of sequences that correspond to refProts and
819 non-chimeric products of short ORFs, we conducted a very comprehensive search for
820 additional alternative sources. This search permitted the discrimination between truly chimeric
821 sequences and those that can be produced from unusual forms of transcripts as follows from
822 the analysis of RNA-Seq data. With an in-house script (Çakır et al., preprint in preparation),
823 we discovered alternative chimeric sources for many peptides and highlighted the role of
824 repeat elements as a potential origin of some chimeric peptides. In summary, the messages
825 sent by these two studies will likely have synergistic effect, which will motivate other research
826 groups for functional characterization of the most interesting candidate peptides.

827 **5.8. Our data support the modern view on the pre-biotic evolution and suggest that**
828 **the ability to undergo “short” frameshifting may be an ancestral feature of all**
829 **genomes**

830 Besides the identification of candidate loci for the production of mosaic and chimeric proteins,
831 our results also indirectly support the modern view on the origin of genomes, and the central
832 role of rRNA in genome evolution. According to the consensus, first genomes and enzymes
833 were composed of single-stranded RNA. These proto-genomes were similar to the modern
834 rRNA in several aspects. They are thought to have been formed by ligation of tRNA-like
835 molecules that acted as monomers, or proto-genes (Root-Bernstein and Root-Bernstein,
836 2015, 2016, 2019; Caetano-Anollés and Caetano-Anollés, 2016; de Farias et al., 2016). This
837 scenario is not purely hypothetical. It is based on experimental observations. Modern rRNA
838 and tRNA molecules have striking features that point to their common evolution. rRNA
839 molecules contain sequences very similar to tRNAs of all 20 usual proteinogenic amino acids
840 (Root-Bernstein and Root-Bernstein, 2015). Furthermore, rRNA-like sequences were found in
841 samples of the poly-adenylated mRNAs, which makes them likely templates for translation.
842 So far, at least 29 such transcripts have been detected in various organisms (e.g., Chooi and
843 Leiby 1981; Divecha and Charleston, 1995; Kermekchiev and Ivanova, 2001; Coelho et al.,
844 2002; Scharf et al., 2005; extensively reviewed in Kong et al., 2008 and Root-Bernstein and
845 Root-Bernstein, 2019). Many of them share similarity with rRNA transcripts detected in this
846 study, far from the putative PRF sites. However, four such sequences make significant same-
847 strand nucleotide alignments with regions very close to the PRF sites: *Mus musculus* testin-2
848 (Divecha and Charleston, 1995); *Homo sapiens* mitochondria-encoded Humanin (Hashimoto
849 et al., 2001); *Candida albicans* mitochondrial protein Tar1p (closely related to *Saccharomyces*
850 *cerevisiae* Tar1p, Coelho et al., 2002); and *Reticulitermes flavipes* rRNA-like mRNA (Scharf
851 et al., 2005). Alignments of these transcripts are shown in Supplementary Dataset S31.
852 Interestingly, Humanin, which is a 24 aa long peptide, is thought to be translated directly from
853 rRNA (Maximov et al., 2002). At the amino acid level, PRF-altORFs located on one tRNA and
854 five rRNA transcripts detected in our study have similarity with annotated proteins of 31
855 different types (Supplementary Datasets S1 and S31), out of which only two have previously
856 been associated with rRNA-like mRNA transcripts: testin-2 (Divecha and Charleston, 1995)
857 and receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase (Kong et al., 2008). Thus, our study expands
858 the knowledge about rRNA-like mRNA transcripts by detecting 29 additional protein types
859 encoded by rRNA-like sequences. So far, there are only three known rRNA-located ORFs
860 related to rRNA-specific functions. This suggests that the majority of rRNA-ORFs with the
861 protein coding capacity may be involved in other biological processes. According to the
862 ribosome-first hypothesis, in rRNA-like proto-genomes, relatively short ORFs overlapped with

863 each other in all reading frames and directions. Thus, the density of protein-coding regions
864 was very high in contrast to modern genomes where only a portion of genes overlap (Root-
865 Bernstein and Root-Bernstein, 2016). Our data support this hypothesis. For example, the
866 analysis of all major transcript types in *M. truncatula* revealed that rRNA has the highest
867 number of ORFs per transcript, when we consider ORFs that have high similarity to known
868 proteins after the conversion of ORFs to amino acid sequences, i.e. conserved altProts. With
869 median length of 120 nt, rRNA transcripts are on average ten times shorter than mRNA
870 transcripts and nearly four times shorter than ncRNA transcripts. Despite the short length,
871 rRNA transcripts contain ca. 31 and ten times more conserved altORFs compared to mRNA
872 and ncRNA, respectively (Table 1). Another remarkable observation concerns the percent
873 identity of ORF translations aligned with annotated proteins from the global collection. The
874 median value of percent identity is the highest for tRNA (100%) followed by rRNA (93.3%), as
875 can be seen in Table 1 and Supplementary Figure S1. The same concerns the median value
876 of query coverage (100% and 94.8%, respectively; the global BLASTP analysis, Table 1). This
877 means that ORF translations from tRNA and rRNA have the highest degree of similarity to
878 annotated proteins, even though they are traditionally considered as non-coding RNA types.
879 Likewise, ORF translations from rRNA have the highest median number of hits per query in
880 the global BLASTP analysis (Supplementary Figures S2 and S3). It is ten times higher
881 compared to mRNA. This supports observations of other researchers according to which
882 rRNA-like sequences are overrepresented in genomes (Root-Bernstein and Root-Bernstein,
883 2019). However, our data confirm this overrepresentation at the protein level, which once
884 again brings rRNA into the spotlight as a potential template for translation. This
885 overrepresentation is also evident at the transcript level, as follows from our analysis of shared
886 subjects in BLASTN (Supplementary Figures S63-S65). In view of these special
887 characteristics of rRNA, it may seem to be not surprising that rRNA transcripts are significantly
888 (25-fold) overrepresented in our dataset (Supplementary Figure S50A). Many of our chimeric
889 models were built using conserved altProts, which were most abundant in rRNA (Table 1).
890 The surprising point is the absence of MS-validated altProts from either rRNA or tRNA in our
891 dataset and the presence of only MS-validated chimeric peptides associated with these
892 transcript types (Supplementary Figure S6). This paradox suggests that some characteristics
893 of rRNA and tRNA distinguish them from other RNA types with regard to PRF. The nearly
894 complete prevalence of PRF value -1 in rRNA and tRNA (Figure 3) further points to the tight
895 evolutionary link between these transcript types. This prevalence is remarkable; the only rRNA
896 transcript associated with multiple frameshifting in our study (MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291) has
897 both PRF sites with value -1 (Supplementary Dataset S4). PRF in tRNA and rRNA has been
898 unknown so far. Likewise, the ability of ncRNA to produce chimeric peptides has never been
899 described before. In our study, 11 such peptides originate from ncRNA. One of eight multi-
900 PRF transcripts illustrated in Supplementary Dataset S4 is ncRNA from mitochondria
901 (MtrunA17_MTg0490971).

902 Since many peptides in our dataset have more than one potential source in the transcriptome,
903 there is a valid question about the true origin of tRNA- and rRNA-derived chimeric MS
904 peptides. To address this concern, we examined the annotation of loci that are alternative
905 sources of non-mRNA-derived chimeric peptides (Supplementary Dataset S1). This analysis
906 revealed that both alternative sources of CP72 (tRNA) are annotated as tRNA. However, they
907 can also be produced by the reverse complement of repeat elements that overlap those tRNA
908 loci. All five non-repeat alternative sources of CP87 (rRNA) are annotated as rRNA. However,
909 this peptide can also be produced by repeat elements. CP1, CP88, CP89, and CP141 have
910 only repeat-element alternative sources. In contrast, CP114 (rRNA) has no detected
911 alternative sources. This indicates that our study is the first one to demonstrate the presence
912 of a unique chimeric rRNA-encoded MS peptide in a proteomic dataset. This is in line with the

913 suggestion that the non-chimeric peptide Humanin (HN1) may be translated directly from
914 rRNA (Hashimoto et al., 2001; Maximov et al., 2002) because the transcript of CP114 shares
915 67.4% nucleotide identity with the transcript of Humanin (Supplementary Dataset S31).
916 Interestingly, CP114 is the only rRNA-chimeric peptide with PRF value +2. All other rRNA-
917 and tRNA-peptides have PRF value -1 (Figure 3). It should be noted that no evidence for the
918 association of repeat elements with PRF value -1 or any other PRF value can be found in our
919 data. Furthermore, among repeat elements mentioned above, only those that correspond to
920 CP88 and CP89 have sufficiently high expression in corresponding organs to be considered
921 as true sources of those rRNA-derived peptides. At the same time, regions around PRF sites
922 in the transcript of CP87, CP88 and CP89 share nucleotide identity with two different rRNA-
923 like mRNA transcripts described earlier (Supplementary Datasets S28 and S31). Together,
924 these observations suggest that CP114 is not the only chimeric peptide translated directly
925 from rRNA (Supplementary Dataset S1). To the best of our knowledge, the detection of rRNA
926 and also ncRNA loci with more than one PRF site per transcript is also unique to our study
927 (Supplementary Datasets S4 and S28).

928 Is there anything special about non-nuclear transcripts when we consider them in the context
929 of PRF? We noticed a trend toward overrepresentation of PRF value +1 in mitochondrial
930 transcripts regardless of the RNA type (Supplementary Figure S11) and also in non-nuclear
931 transcripts combined (Figure 4). Remarkably, the trend is opposite for nuclear transcripts,
932 where PRF value +1 is underrepresented. Two out of eight multi-PRF transcripts shown in
933 Supplementary Dataset S4 have mitochondrial origin, one mRNA and one ncRNA. Both
934 transcripts contain exclusively +1 PRF sites. Chloroplast and mitochondrial transcripts are
935 significantly overrepresented in the dataset (19-fold and 12-fold, respectively; Supplementary
936 Figure S50). These observations reflect the origin of these organelles and highlight the PRF-
937 related difference between nuclear (eukaryotic) and non-nuclear (prokaryotic) transcripts. The
938 biological significance of this difference deserves close attention. It is possible that “short”
939 frameshifts that appear to be associated with transcripts of ancient origin in our study (-1
940 frameshifts in rRNA and +1 frameshifts in non-nuclear transcripts) represent the ancestral
941 feature whereas “long” frameshifts evolved later. Earlier, we emphasized that prokaryotes are
942 likely to have tremendously benefited from mosaic translation and from PRF in general given
943 the absence of alternative splicing and relatively small genome sizes. In this respect, they are
944 close to viruses where PRF is essential for survival. We hypothesize that the ability to undergo
945 PRF has been an intrinsic feature of all genomes from the very beginning. Conceivably, at
946 some early point in the evolution, it has been harnessed for mosaic translation. This process
947 must have diversified proteomes of primitive organisms because it utilizes the genomic space
948 more efficiently and inventively. This “new dimension” of the proteomes probably facilitated
949 the gradual increase in complexity and adaptability of organisms, which ensured their
950 evolutionary success (Çakır et al., 2023).

951 **6. Conclusions**

952 We hope that our study will constitute a rich resource for many discoveries associated with
953 PRF and translation from non-mRNA transcript types. In a broader sense, we anticipate that
954 this work will seed a new field of genetic studies that will consider the nearly infinite protein-
955 coding potential of transcripts due to multiple PRF events. We also hope that many genetic
956 diseases so far not explained with traditional views on the proteome complexity will ultimately
957 find their cures when chimeric and mosaic proteins in eukaryotes will be discovered at a large
958 scale. Likewise, the progress in the development of more resilient and more productive crops
959 will benefit from the discovery of chimeric and mosaic proteins involved in efficient stress
960 responses and other agriculturally important traits. We believe, major advances in nanopore
961 sequencing of proteins will enable the direct detection of chimeric and mosaic proteins, which

962 will leave no doubt about their composite origin. As more evidence supporting the conclusions
963 of our study becomes available, it is possible that our view on the protein-coding potential in
964 higher eukaryotes will undergo a transition from two-dimensional (refProt plus altProt) to multi-
965 dimensional (refProt plus numerous multi-frame chimeric products). We are looking forward
966 to further development of this concept, which is currently in its infancy.

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976 Project administration, Funding acquisition.

977 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

978 The authors declare no competing interest relevant to this study.

979 **Data availability**

980 Sequences of MS-supported chimeric models, their corresponding MS peptides and
981 transcripts, as well as genomic DNA, alignments, and other relevant features with detailed
982 annotation are available in Geneious® format in the online version of this article. Chimeric
983 protein model sequences used as MS search databases, certificates of analysis, and
984 peptide/protein report files from MS searches are available as separate supplementary
985 datasets (Supplementary Datasets S32-S36) in the online version of this article.
986 Corresponding files for the conservation evidence and MS-validation of altProts that were the
987 basis for modeling of chimeric proteins will be published later in a paper with the focus on
988 altProts. Another article will contain our meta-analysis on 627 *M. truncatula* genes studied with
989 loss-of-function approaches and will address MS-supported and conserved altORFs located
990 on already studied genes. Two dedicated software articles will describe the details and provide
991 the codes of in-house scripts generated for this study: one for the modeling of chimeric
992 peptides and the other one for the detection of alternative chimeric sources (Çakır et al.,
993 preprints in preparation). Data on more than 18,600 conserved altORFs, 805 MS-supported
994 altORFs, 156 chimeric peptides, and their non-RE alternative sources will be integrated into
995 the *M. truncatula* genome portal MtrunA17r5.0-ANR as a separate track. The complete set of
996 data related to this preprint is available in the Zenodo repository.

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1362 **Table 1.** Statistics on altProts with at least one hit in the global BLASTP analysis after the
1363 application of the filter¹

Statistic	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
Number of transcripts	44,624	5,657	62	974
Median length of transcripts, nt	1,280	413	120	75
Total number of altORFs ²	8,718	3,549	385	426
altORFs per transcript	0.20	0.63	6.21	0.44
Transcripts per altORF	5.12	1.59	0.16	2.29
Median length of altProts, aa	53.0	47.0	45.0	25.0
Median length of alignment, aa	38.0	36.0	40.0	24.0
Median percent identity	87.5	91.4	93.3	100.0
Median percent query coverage	82.5	84.5	94.8	100.0
altORFs longer than 300 nt	795	215	15	0
altORFs longer than 600 nt	33	27	3	0

¹BLASTP filter settings: e-value ≤ 0.001; percent identity ≥ 70.

²There are 13,078 of such altORFs combined from the RNA types mentioned here.

1364

1365 **Figures and figure legends**

1366

1367 **Figure 1.** Three candidate mosaic proteins deduced from chimeric MS peptides. A, Mosaic
 1368 protein 1 translated from transcript MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 (the locus annotated as a
 1369 putative protein-synthesizing GTPase). B, Mosaic protein 2 translated from transcript
 1370 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 (the locus annotated as a putative ribulose-bisphosphate
 1371 carboxylase, RuBisCo). C, Mosaic protein 3 translated from the same transcript
 1372 MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461. Mosaic proteins 2 and 3 differ by one amino acid around the -2
 1373 PRF site (red-boxed R and K, respectively). The upper portion of each figure depicts a
 1374 corresponding transcript with ORFs mapped and scaled relative to the whole transcript length.
 1375 Asterisks represent positions of PRF events. The text in blue describes the PRF value,
 1376 and subtype of each frameshifting event. Interpretation example: -2 (2r→3a) refers to a
 1377 frameshift with value minus 2 from a refORF in frame 2 (yellow) to an altORF in frame 3 (pink).
 1378 The green triangle indicates the position of the first in-frame translational start codon (AUG).

1379

1380 **Figure 2.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides in different groups according to PRF
 1381 values. A, Four separate groups of PRF. B, Two combined groups of PRF. Expected values
 1382 were calculated based on the numbers of corresponding chimeric protein models (non-
 1383 redundant counts in Supplementary Table S9, 469,600 models in total). There is no significant
 1384 difference between the observed and expected proportions for the separate groups (A) and a
 1385 significant difference ($p = 0.016$; the chi-square test for goodness-of-fit) for the combined
 1386 groups (B). The distribution of PRF values within individual groups in A and B is not

1387 significantly different from the uniform distribution. However, the distribution of observed
 1388 values in B is significantly different from the uniform distribution ($p = 0.025$; the chi-square test
 1389 for homogeneity): PRF values with the negative sign are significantly overrepresented in the
 1390 dataset.

1391
 1392 **Figure 3.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides in different groups based on the RNA type
 1393 and the PRF value. The Fisher's exact test shows significant association between the RNA
 1394 type and the PRF value ($p = 0.007$ with tRNA included, $p = 7.024E-07$ with tRNA excluded).
 1395 Within individual RNA groups, the distribution of PRF values is significantly different from the
 1396 uniform distribution in one case indicated with an asterisk (the Exact Multinomial Test, $p =$
 1397 0.019). With PRF values -1 and +2 only, the difference is not significant. Note the absence of
 1398 certain PRF values from ncRNA and rRNA. Remarkably, the only PRF value in tRNA is the
 1399 same as the most frequent PRF value in rRNA.

1400

1401 **Figure 4.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides based on the genomic location of their
 1402 primary-source genes and the PRF value. “Nuclear”: Chromosome 0 (unmapped loci) to
 1403 Chromosome 8. “Non-nuclear”: chloroplasts and mitochondria. There is no significant
 1404 association between the genomic location and the PRF value. Within individual genomic
 1405 locations, the distribution of PRF values is significantly different from the uniform
 1406 distribution in one case indicated with an asterisk (the Exact Multinomial Test, $p = 0.018$). PRF
 1407 events with value +1 are significantly underrepresented in nuclear transcripts and non-significantly
 1408 overrepresented in chloroplasts and mitochondria.

1409

1410 **Figure 5.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides based on the PRF type and value. Each
 1411 PRF type has only two possible values: one positive and one negative. There is significant
 1412 association between the PRF type and the PRF value based on the chi-square test ($p = 0.007$,
 1413 a two-category test with categories of the same absolute value combined). Within individual
 1414 groups, the distribution is significantly different from the uniform distribution in two cases
 1415 indicated with asterisks: 1→3 and 2→3 (the chi-square test for homogeneity, p -values are

1416 0.011 and 0.005, respectively). Backward PRF is more frequent for the shift from any frame
 1417 to frame 3.

1418

1419 **Figure 6.** Distribution of 156 MS-supported models in three folding categories based on two
 1420 aspects of the PRF value. A, grouping by the direction of PRF (minus, backward frameshifts;
 1421 plus, forward frameshifts). B, grouping by the length of PRF (± 1 , “short” frameshifts; ± 2 , “long”
 1422 frameshifts). There is no significant association in A and B. Within individual folding categories,
 1423 the distribution is significantly different from the uniform distribution in two cases indicated with
 1424 asterisks (the chi-square test for homogeneity, p-values are 0.035 and 0.014 for A and B,
 1425 respectively). Backward PRF values are significantly overrepresented in chimeric peptides
 1426 with predicted alpha-helices. Beta-sheet structures are three times more abundant in the
 1427 models with “long” PRF values.

1428

1429 **Figure 7.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides in 16 biological samples depending on the
 1430 PRF value. The counts are not additive because some chimeric peptides were identified in
 1431 multiple samples. No chimeric peptides were detected in samples N28 and PhD. The PRF
 1432 value is significantly associated with the sample (the Fisher’s exact test with a simulated p-
 1433 value, $p = 0.010$). Within individual samples, the distribution of PRF values is significantly
 1434 different from the uniform distribution in three cases indicated with asterisks. P-values of the
 1435 chi-square test for homogeneity are as follows: 0.036 (B) and 0.040 (Se). The significance in
 1436 sample RoC was assessed with the Exact Multinomial Test ($p = 0.019$). No chimeric peptides
 1437 with PRF values -1 and +1 were found in samples RoC and RoD. Chimeric peptides with PRF

1438 values +1 and +2 are absent from sample PhC. Sample B lacks chimeric peptides with PRF
 1439 value +1.

1440
 1441 **Figure 8.** Distribution of 156 chimeric MS peptides in different PRF categories depending on
 1442 the PRF type and subtype. r→a, PRF from refORF to altORF; a→r, PRF from altORF to
 1443 refORF; a1→a2, PRF from altORF1 to altORF2, where altORF1 starts upstream of altORF2;
 1444 a2→a1, PRF from altORF2 to altORF1, where altORF1 starts upstream of altORF2. There is
 1445 no significant association between the PRF type and the PRF subtype. Proportion pairs in
 1446 which the distribution is significantly different from the uniform distribution are marked with
 1447 asterisks. P-values of the chi-square test for homogeneity of two proportions: *0.034; **0.005.
 1448 In PRF type 1→2, PRF subtype r→a is significantly more frequent than PRF subtype a→r. In
 1449 PRF type 2→1, it is the other way around, which means refORFs involved in PRF are
 1450 associated with frame 1 and altORFs with frame 2 in those two categories. There is a non-
 1451 significant trend of the same kind in PRF types 2→3 and 3→2, where refORFs are associated
 1452 with frame 2.

1453 **Supporting information**

1454 This preprint contains supplementary materials: Supplementary Results (1), Supplementary
 1455 Figures (67), Supplementary Tables (9), and Supplementary Datasets (36).

1456 **Supplementary Results**

1457 Supplementary Results are available as a separate file.

1458 **Supplementary Figures**

1459 Supplementary Figures are available as a separate file.

1460 **Supplementary Tables**

1461 Supplementary Tables are available as a separate file.

1462 **Supplementary Table S1.** Statistics on all ORFs 60 nt or longer grouped by RNA type.

1463 **Supplementary Table S2.** Statistics on altProts with at least one hit in the global BLASTP
 1464 analysis before the application of the filter.

1465 **Supplementary Table S3.** Numbers of altProts before and after the elimination of queries
1466 with less than 70% identity to annotated proteins.

1467 **Supplementary Table S4.** Distribution of transcripts in different categories based on RNA
1468 type, cellular localization, mass spectrometry (MS) support of altORFs, and conservation of
1469 altORF translation products.

1470 **Supplementary Table S5.** Redundant counts of chimeric protein models, shown per altProt
1471 type, transcript type, and programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) value.

1472 **Supplementary Table S6.** Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with
1473 altORFs that are MS-supported and conserved at the same time, shown per transcript type
1474 and PRF value.

1475 **Supplementary Table S7.** Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with MS-
1476 supported altORFs, shown per proteomic study and PRF value.

1477 **Supplementary Table S8.** Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with
1478 conserved altORFs, shown per transcript type and PRF value.

1479 **Supplementary Table S9.** Non-redundant counts of chimeric protein models, shown per
1480 altProt type, transcript type, and PRF value.

1481 **Supplementary Datasets**

1482 Supplementary Datasets are available as individual files.

1483 **Supplementary Dataset S1.** Master table. A master table that summarizes various
1484 parameters of 156 chimeric MS peptides validated in this study and characteristics of their
1485 corresponding transcripts.

1486 **Supplementary Dataset S2.** Graphical summary. A graphical summary on alignments
1487 between 156 chimeric peptide models (CPs) and corresponding MS peptides (left) together
1488 with transcript models (right) that feature the transcript type, length in nucleotides, and
1489 relative positions of ORFs (to scale) involved in the production of CPs.

1490 **Supplementary Dataset S3.** Relevant sequences with detailed annotation. This Geneious®-
1491 formatted dataset contains sequences of 156 MS-supported chimeric models (CPs), their
1492 corresponding MS peptides and transcripts, as well as genomic DNA, alignments, and other
1493 informative features with detailed annotation.

1494 **Supplementary Dataset S4.** Primary-source transcripts associated with multiple PRF
1495 events. Eight primary-source transcripts associated with multiple PRF events.

1496 **Supplementary Dataset S5.** Mosaic proteins. Three candidate mosaic proteins deduced
1497 from chimeric MS peptides.

1498 **Supplementary Dataset S6.** Folding of mosaic proteins.

1499 **Supplementary Dataset S7.** Folding of chimeric protein models Part 1. A graphical
1500 summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 1-50.

1501 **Supplementary Dataset S7.** Folding of chimeric protein models Part 2. A graphical
1502 summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 51-100.

1503 **Supplementary Dataset S7.** Folding of chimeric protein models Part 3. A graphical
1504 summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 101-156.

1505 **Supplementary Dataset S7**. Folding of chimeric protein models Part 4 Alpha-helices only. A
1506 graphical summary on folding predictions for 90 MS-supported chimeric peptide models
1507 (CPs) that contain alpha-helices and no beta-sheets.

1508 **Supplementary Dataset S7**. Folding of chimeric protein models Part 5 Beta-sheets only. A
1509 graphical summary on folding predictions for 24 MS-supported chimeric peptide models
1510 (CPs) that contain beta-sheets regardless of the presence of alpha-helices.

1511 **Supplementary Dataset S8**. Alpha helices vs PRF value. Distribution of 90 alpha-helix-
1512 forming models of chimeric MS peptides in four categories based on the PRF position
1513 relative to the helices.

1514 **Supplementary Dataset S9**. Alpha helices inside only vs PRF value. Distribution of 72 MS-
1515 supported models based on the position of PRF sites inside alpha-helices.

1516 **Supplementary Dataset S10**. Beta sheets vs PRF value. Distribution of 24 MS-supported
1517 chimeric peptide models with predicted beta-sheets in four categories based on the position
1518 of PRF sites relative to the beta-sheets.

1519 **Supplementary Dataset S11**. Overlapping genes. The genomic landscape at and around
1520 the primary-source loci of 156 MS-supported chimeric peptides.

1521 **Supplementary Dataset S12**. Nucleotide alignments of random RNA samples. Distribution
1522 of percent nucleotide identity values of 45 pairwise alignments among ten randomly chosen
1523 transcripts per RNA category.

1524 **Supplementary Dataset S13**. Homology groups 1 to 10. Homology groups based on
1525 pairwise nucleotide alignments with percent identity values 56 and above.

1526 **Supplementary Dataset S14**. Alignments among 34 primary-source transcripts with
1527 detectable similarity. A graphical summary on nucleotide alignments among all 34 primary-
1528 source transcripts that have the global or the local similarity to each other.

1529 **Supplementary Dataset S15**. Summary on sequences with shared subjects in the BLASTN
1530 analysis. Summary on the primary-source transcript sequences with shared subjects in the
1531 BLASTN analysis and sequences that have direct similarity over the entire length.

1532 **Supplementary Dataset S16**. Sequences with shared subjects in the BLASTN analysis.
1533 Primary-source transcript sequences with shared subjects in the BLASTN analysis.

1534 **Supplementary Dataset S17**. Selected RNA-Seq runs. Fifty RNA-Seq runs selected for the
1535 identification of non-chimeric alternative sources of 156 MS-supported chimeric peptides.

1536 **Supplementary Dataset S18**. Details of the RNA-Seq analysis.

1537 **Supplementary Dataset S19**. RNA-Seq read alignments. A graphical summary on
1538 alignments between transcripts of 15 MS-supported chimeric peptides and RNA-Seq reads
1539 from 50 selected RNA-Seq runs.

1540 **Supplementary Dataset S20**. RNA-Seq reads with exact matches in more than one run.

1541 **Supplementary Dataset S21**. Sequencing adapters and primers.

1542 **Supplementary Dataset S22**. Non-repeat-element alternative chimeric sources. Non-
1543 repeat-element alternative chimeric sources of 156 MS-supported chimeric peptides.

1544 **Supplementary Dataset S23**. Repeat-element alternative chimeric sources. Repeat-
1545 element alternative chimeric and non-chimeric sources of 156 MS-supported chimeric
1546 peptides.

1547 **Supplementary Dataset S24**. Summary on alternative sources of chimeric peptides. This
1548 dataset summarizes the information from Supplementary Datasets S22 and S23.

1549 **Supplementary Dataset S25**. Non-overlapping repeat elements. A list of 70 alternative-
1550 source repeat elements that do not overlap with any locus at the putative PRF sites.

1551 **Supplementary Dataset S26**. Expression profiles of non-overlapping repeat elements.
1552 Expression profiles of ten non-overlapping repeat elements that have log₂ TMM values
1553 above zero.

1554 **Supplementary Dataset S27**. Expression profiles of 156 primary-source transcripts.

1555 **Supplementary Dataset S28**. Alternative-source transcripts associated with multiple PRF
1556 events.

1557 **Supplementary Dataset S29**. Summary on the most relevant statistically significant
1558 observations.

1559 **Supplementary Dataset S30**. Summary on the most relevant statistically significant
1560 associations.

1561 **Supplementary Dataset S31**. Alignments of rRNA transcripts with known rRNA-like mRNA
1562 transcripts.

1563 **Supplementary Dataset S32**. All chimeric protein models (redundant).

1564 **Supplementary Dataset S33**. All chimeric protein models (unique).

1565 **Supplementary Dataset S34**. Chimeric proteins modeled with conserved altProts
1566 (redundant).

1567 **Supplementary Dataset S35**. Chimeric proteins modeled with MS-supported altProts
1568 (redundant).

1569 **Supplementary Dataset S36**. MS reports and certificates of analysis.